

USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES

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ANNOTATION: This article talks about the composition of natural sciences, the purpose of studying sciences, and the use of innovative methods in teaching sciences.

KEY WORDS: laws of society, "Objects of Nature", "Cluster" method, "6 x 6" method, "Brainstorming" method

Now in the educational system of Uzbekistan, from the 2021-2022 academic year, natural sciences, which include natural sciences, have been introduced in grades 1-6. At the same time, natural sciences (SCIENCE) are taught in the 1st-2nd grade "The world around us", in the 3rd-4th grade "Natural science", and in the upper grades there are 4 separate subjects, i.e. geography, biology, physics (from the 6th grade), chemistry (from the 7th grade) combines subjects. The advantages and importance of natural sciences (SCIENCE) is that through science, the student understands the integral, inseparable, wholeness of the world, develops a scientific worldview, and develops research skills. As a result, the possibility of successful participation in international studies such as PISA and TIMSS increases. The project of the National Curriculum for Natural Sciences (SCIENCE) was created and discussed by the Republican Education Center under the Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

MAIN PART Natural sciences are sciences that study the substances that make up a person, his health, as well as the entire environment: soil, atmosphere, the earth in general, space, nature, all living and inanimate objects, and their changes. The main task of the block-module of natural and economic sciences is to illuminate the complex of scientific and practical knowledge about the phenomena and processes occurring in nature, the stages of development of living organisms, the effects of mankind on the laws of nature and society. The

extent to which the student's internal motivation is formed, his interest in natural and economic sciences, his understanding of environmental problems and the ability to make important decisions in solving them, and his ability to analyze the impact on the natural and social environment are important 21 "Natural Sciences in the Modern World: Theoretical and Practical Research" scientific, remote, online conference named Mutual integration of sciences should lead students to understand nature as a whole being, a single view of the universe. At the same time, students should understand the negative and positive effects of human activity on nature, global environmental problems at the scale of time and space, and a sense of responsibility towards nature. and aims to educate a competent person who can contribute to the development of society. Teaching natural sciences as a separate subject starts from the 1st grade. The educational material is combined into the topics of "Natural bodies", "Plant and animal world", "Keeping our health" and "Ecology". The program on natural sciences allows schoolchildren of younger age to learn not only the beauty and wealth of nature, but also the nature of our republic. In the teaching of natural sciences, attention is paid to the formation and expansion of students' scientific and natural worldviews, and to the explanation of the topic of each lesson in teaching logical thinking. In the process of students' individual performance of tasks, their mental activity is involved, confidence in their knowledge, strength and abilities increases. As a result, each person develops at the level of their potential. Time is effectively used in cognitive activities organized in this way. As a result, the effectiveness of education increases. Students' cognitive activities are organized individually in lessons conducted using modern pedagogical technologies of education. "Cluster" method. This method helps to create conditions for students to freely and openly think about problems (topics) and freely express their personal opinions. The "Cluster" method requires the identification of a structure that allows thinking about the connections between different ideas. This method is a form of thinking that is not directed to a specific object. Its use is carried out in connection with the principle of human brain activity. The "Cluster" method can be used in the course of training organized individually or in groups with students. In group training, this method is manifested in the form of a set of ideas expressed by group members. This creates an opportunity to harmonize the ideas put forward by each member of the group and to find connections between them. "6 x 6" method. With the help of the "6 x 6" method, it is possible to solve a certain task or issue by involving 36 students in a certain activity at the same time, as well as

to determine the capabilities of each member of the group, to learn their views. Based on this method, the 22nd scientific, remote, online conference entitled "Natural Sciences in the Modern World: Theoretical and Practical Research" will discuss the problem raised by the teacher in 6 groups of 6 participants in each lesson. At the end of the set time, the teacher reorganizes the 6 groups. Each of the newly formed groups has one representative from the previous 6 groups. The members of the newly formed group report to their teammates the conclusion presented by the previous group as a solution to the problem and discuss these solutions together. The advantages of the "6x6" method are as follows: - it encourages each member of the group to be active; - ensures the expression of personal views by them; - develops the skills of listening to the opinions of other members of the group; - it teaches to be able to generalize a given idea, as well as to defend one's own opinion. The most important thing is that for a short time (15-20 minutes) each student works both as a participant in the discussion and as a speaker. In the classes where this method is used, there is an opportunity to discuss one or more topics (tunammo) by groups. The use of the "6 x 6" method in the educational process requires the teacher to have activity, pedagogical skills, and the ability to form groups in accordance with the purpose. Improper formation of groups may cause tasks or tasks not to be solved correctly. Using this method, classes are organized in the following order: 1. Before the class, the teacher places 6 chairs around 6 tables. 2. 6 different tasks are written on 6 sheets. Roman numerals from I to VI are written on the sheets. These sheets are placed on each of the 6 tables. 3. Students are divided into 6 groups by the teacher. The teacher divides the students into groups as follows. Each student is invited to take one of the sheets numbered from 1 to 36. These sheets show the table number with Roman numerals. Each student takes a seat on the chair placed around the table indicated by the Roman numeral on the sheet of his choice. 4. After the students have settled down, the teacher sets a certain time (5-10 minutes) for completing the tasks placed on the table, and announces the start of the discussion process. 5. The teacher monitors the activity of the groups, gives advice and guidance to the group members in the necessary places. At the end of the allotted time, he asks the groups to finish their discussions. 6. When the time for the discussion ends, the teacher re-forms the groups. Special attention is paid to having one representative from each of the previous 6 groups in each newly formed group. After the students have changed their places, within the specified time (5-10 minutes), the members of

the group have assigned the task to their previous groups. and they tell their groupmates about its solution.

In this order, they discuss the received conclusions and come to a final conclusion. It is advisable to conduct the "6x6" method in order to repeat and strengthen the topics covered in certain chapters or quarters of the academic year. The "Brainstorming" method is a widely used method for solving problems on a specific topic. This method encourages students to develop certain skills and abilities to think broadly and comprehensively about a problem, as well as to use their imaginations and ideas positively. In the course of the lesson organized with the help of this method, there is an opportunity to find some original solutions to optional problems. The main goal of using this method is to encourage students to think broadly and deeply about the problem.

CONCLUSION The educational subjects of biology, nature and geography, physics, chemistry, the basics of economic knowledge and the basics of entrepreneurship are of great importance in the formation of students' scientific knowledge about nature, in the formation of their worldviews and in the development of their thinking.

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